

THE IMPORTANCE OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IN COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Gender differences in dishonesty and mistrust have been reported across cultures and linked to stereotypes about more trustworthy and trusting females. Here we focus on fundamental issues of trust-based communication that may be affected by gender: the decisions whether to honestly deliver private information and whether to trust that this delivered information is honest. Using laboratory experiments that model trust-based strategic communication and response, we examined the relationship between gender, gender stereotypes, and gender discriminative lies and challenges. Drawing from a student sample, we presented males and females (N = 80) with incentivized stereotype elicitation tasks that reveal their expectations of lies and challenges from each gender, followed by a series of strategic communication interactions within and between genders. Before interacting, both genders stereotyped females as more trustworthy (expected to send more honest messages) and more trusting (expected to accept and not challenge others' messages) than males, in accord with cross-cultural gender differences. In best response to these stereotypes, both genders discriminately accepted or challenged messages based on the sender's gender. However, we find no differences between males' and females' overall rates of lies and challenges. After learning the results of their strategic interactions, males

and females revised their stereotypes about lies and challenges expected of each gender; these stereotype revisions resulted in greater predictive accuracy and less disparate gender discrimination. This suggests an important facultative feature of human trust-based communication and gender stereotyping: while the delivery and trust of private information is informed by gender stereotypes, these stereotypes are recalibrated with experience.

Keywords: gender, stereotype, trust, discrimination, strategic communication

Gender differences. In the last decade, research has emerged examining whether gender affects individual behavior and behavior in interpersonal interactions across a variety of settings. While a comprehensive review of the literature is outside the scope of this paper, we review several examples of research relevant to trust-based communication.

In individual tasks, men are more likely to lie to secure a gain and also likely to be more dishonest in the magnitude of their lies (Friesen & Gangadharan, 2012; Grosch & Rau, 2017; Houser, Vetter, & Winter, 2012). Women are more likely to tell white lies (with altruistic effects) than men (Erat & Gneezy, 2012). In strategic sender-receiver interactions, women show greater aversion to lying for a smaller monetary benefit than men (Capraro, 2018; Childs, 2012; Dreber & Johannesson, 2008; Erat & Gneezy, 2012), but when larger stakes are available, no gender differences are seen (Childs, 2012).

While gender differences are noted in several domains of strategic interaction, there is less consistent support for a gender-differentiated account of gender discrimination in trust or trustworthiness (Croson & Gneezy, 2009; Eckel & Grossman, 2008). From survey responses, Shaub (1996) finds that while auditors (who decide whether to invest in veracity checks) characterize their

female clients as more trustworthy than their male clients, this does not predict their likelihood of trusting female over male clients. Controlling for experience and availability of ethical information, Owoso (2002) finds no gender differences among practicing auditors in detecting lies despite gender differences in sensitivity to ethical issues. While trust based investments show no gender differences, women tend to be more reciprocal than men in anonymous trust games (Chaudhuri & Sbai, 2011; Croson & Buchan, 1999). In trust games where participants knew one another's gender, there was no difference in likelihood of trusting males over females, or showing more trustworthiness to a particular gender (Buchan, Croson, & Solnick, 2008).

Empirical research has documented that information asymmetry contributes to inefficient allocations between spouses (Udry, 1996; Vogler, Lyolette, & Wiggins, 2008; Vogler & Pahl, 1993, 1994). Noncooperative resource allocation in migrant households also results from longer distances between spouses and for longer periods they spend apart (Chen, 2006). Among Tsimane forager-farmers with recent market integration, husbands report a wage that is eight percent higher than what their wives report being aware of, suggesting men lie to their spouses about their true earnings so as to divert the unreported earnings towards extra-marital interests (Stieglitz, Kaplan, Gurven, Winking, & Tayo, 2011). Similar results are revealed by field experiments in the Philippines where men but not women hide income from their wives (Ashraf, 2009). No such gender differences are observed in Ghana where both husbands and wives chose to allocate private windfalls in ways that were either difficult to monitor or to reverse if discovered by the other spouse (Castilla & Walker, 2013).

Research on tax behavior suggests that women are more likely to cooperate with honest reporting and to evade to a lesser extent than men (Hasseldine, 2002). Tax compliance experiments also find that men are less likely to file honest reports and more likely to evade (Kastlunger, Dressler, Kirchler, Mittone,

& Voracek, 2010).

In this study, we use an instrument that can directly measure lying and veracity-challenge behavior in a strategic setting and determine whether senders or receivers practice gender discrimination. By directly assessing participants' stereotypes about genders they interact with, and directly measuring behavior conditional on the interaction partner's gender and role, we can provide direct measures of gender-based discrimination.

Gender stereotypes and discrimination. Gender is a salient piece of potentially predictive information that people often have access to when developing expectations about others. Among stereotyped social categories (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity, and social class), gender is one of the most accurate and universally agreed-upon stereotypes (Jussim, Cain, Crawford, Harber, & Cohen, 2009; Löckenhoff et al., 2014). Males are perceived as agentic: with the expectation that they are more likely to show assertiveness (e.g. acting in accordance with expectations) and to pursue risky opportunities (e.g. lying or challenging, when the outcome might be costly), while females are perceived as more “communal”, expected to show more warmth and care for others (Eagly, 2009; Ellemers, 2018). Stereotype differences in emphasis placed upon agency versus communality reflect gender expectations. Males are expected to be selfish, mistrusting, untrustworthy, risk-taking, and confident, while females are seen as helping, ethical, cautious, trusting and trustworthy (Eagly & Crowley, 1986; Orbell, Dawes, & Schwartz-Shea, 1994).

Gender stereotyping is ubiquitous in decision making, helping us identify, interpret, and remember information about others (Amodio, 2014). In a dictator game experiment, systematic differences in stereotyped gender expectations may contribute to systematic differences in altruistic behavior (Rigdon & Levine, 2018). In an experiment with aligned incentives among participants in groups, people who held stronger gender stereotypes about their expected abilities in

gender-incongruent performance categories were less likely to contribute their ideas to a group (Coffman, 2014).

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